

Bidirectional Dual Active Bridge Converter for EV Applications

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Abstract—This paper describes a single pulse-width modulation control strategy using the Single Pulse-Width Modulation (SPWM) method with a soft-switching technique for a wide range of output voltages from a bidirectional Dual-Active Bridge (DAB) converter. This method selects two typical inductor current waveforms for soft-switching and proposes a rule that makes it possible to achieve soft-switching without any compensation algorithm from the waveforms. In addition, both the step-up and step-down conditions are analyzed. This paper verifies that the leakage inductance is independent from the rule, which makes it easier to apply in DAB converters. An integrated algorithm, which includes step-up and step-down techniques, is proposed. The system efficiency is experimentally verified to be from 85.6% to 97.5% over the entire range.

Keywords—SPWM Strategy, Boost Mode, Buck Mode, Switching Frequency

I. INTRODUCTION

A combination of the growing concern about the potential consequences of global warming, the high volatility of fossil fuel prices and the need to improve security in relation to the global energy supply, has motivated an increase in the priority to develop integrated policies that aim to address these issues on the global stage. More specifically, to reduce dependence on non-renewable fossil fuel and the consequential amount of greenhouse gas emission, the demand for Electric Vehicles has grown rapidly, especially across the last two decades. With the growth of electricity demand, concern about environmental issues and possible energy crisis, hybrid systems based on renewable energy resources have been received more attentions. All renewable energy resources have an inherent feature that varies randomly, resulting in an energy storage system is needed to provide clean and safe power for loads. Bidirectional DC/DC converters as a key component in hybrid systems, interface between renewable energy resources such as a fuel cells or a photovoltaic (PV) arrays and energy storage elements such as a batteries and super capacitors. They are used in many applications such as hybrid electric vehicles, distribution systems, electric aircrafts and uninterruptable power supplies [1-2].

Conventional full bridge dc/dc converters can be used but are not easily scaled to higher power levels because of system parasitics and switching losses. Transformer leakage inductance, stray loop inductance and diode recovery pose significant problems for conventional converters. The Dual Active Bridge or DAB converter is well known and has been built at power levels in the hundreds of kilowatts. The DAB converter offers a ‘minimal’ topology, using two semiconductor bridges, dc side capacitors and the isolating transformer. The bidirectional DC-DC converter has many different configurations, but it can mainly be classified into two major groups based on the galvanic isolation. The first group is the non-isolated type and it can be achieved by applying interleaving techniques, switched-capacitor converters, or by using coupled-inductors. In cases where a high voltage ratio and isolation are not required, the non-isolated type is always applied owing to advantages such as simple topology and control scheme [3-5]. Another group is the isolated type. This type contains a high frequency transformer is employed which provides the voltage gain ratio and galvanic isolation. The target converter in this thesis is a form of isolated bidirectional DC/DC converter [6-8]. The primary objective of the work is to reduce conduction loss by using proper PWM control for EV application.

II. BIDIRECTIONAL DUAL ACTIVE BRIDGE CONVERTER

The DAB comprises HF transformer coupled primary and secondary side full bridges, performing the DC output voltage (V_{DC2}) regulation while maintaining unity power factor at the AC side by actively wave shaping the line current $i_{DC1}(t)$ as shown in Fig. 1. Therefore, they produce phase shifted edge resonant square wave voltages $v_1(t)$ and $v_2(t)$ at the terminals of the HF AC-link (inductor L and HF transformer, resulting in an inductor current $i_L(t)$). The objective of the design will also be developed. The two MOSFETs must be driven in a complimentary manner with a small dead time to avoid shoot through.

Fig. 1 Configuration of Bidirectional DAB Converter

The DAB converter has three control parameters α , β and ϕ . Here, α and β represents half of the zero-voltage intervals at the primary and secondary sides, respectively. The phase difference between the primary and secondary voltages is written as ϕ . Note that the three parameters are completely utilized with pulse-width based modulation strategies. Meanwhile, only the phase difference is employed for the PSM strategies. The input voltage is fixed at 750V while the output voltage ranges from 580V to 820V. Here the nominal output voltage is 750V. As a result, that the turns ratio of the transformer is set to 1:1. The rated operating power is 50kW. The auxiliary inductance is set to 38 μH and the switching frequency is selected as 10kHz. The inductance is considered as the peak inductor current at the maximum operating power, and the peak inductor current is calculated from the SPWM modelling equation.

A. Dual-Active Bridge - Switching Sequence

In a single-phase, dual-active bridge, primary and secondary bridges are controlled simultaneously. All switches operate at 50% duty ratio. The diagonal switches turn on and turn off together so that the output of each bridge is a square wave. The switching sequence of the converter is elaborated in detail in this section. The switching sequence is divided into four intervals based on the inductor current waveform and phase shift between the voltages at the primary and secondary of the transformer. The switching sequence of DAB during different intervals are shown in Fig. 2.

During interval 1, switches Q1 and Q4 in the primary and switches Q6 and Q7 in the secondary conduct current and the inductor current waveform is both positive and negative. The voltage across the primary, V_p , is equal to V_1 , and the voltage across the secondary, V_s , is equal to V_2 . The difference between these voltages appears across the leakage inductor, and the slope of the current during this interval can be approximated by the following Equation.

$$\left(\frac{di}{dt}\right) = \frac{V_1 + V_2}{L}$$

During interval 2, the inductor current is positive. The voltage across the transformer primary is positive and is equal to V_1 , and the voltage across the secondary winding is positive and is equal to V_2 . Hence, the difference of these two voltages appears across the leakage inductor, and the slope of the rising current during this interval can be calculated by Equation.

$$\left(\frac{di}{dt}\right) = \frac{V_1 - V_2}{L}$$

Fig. 2 Switching sequence of Bidirectional DAB Converter

During this interval, switches Q1 and Q4 remain turned on, but as the voltage across the secondary is now V_2 with the inductor current positive, switches Q5 and Q8 turn on to conduct current. There is a small dead time period between the turn off of Q6 and Q7 and the turn on of Q5 and Q8.

During interval 3, the inductor current starts ramping down from its positive peak to a negative value. In this interval, the voltage across the primary is $-V_1$, and the voltage across the secondary is V_2 . The difference of these voltages, which is $(-V_1-V_2)$, appears across the inductor. Hence, the current ramps down with a negative slope as shown in the following Equation.

$$\left(\frac{di}{dt}\right) = \frac{V_1 + V_2}{L}$$

During this interval, switches Q5 and Q8 continue to remain turned on, but as the voltage across the primary is now $-V_1$, switches Q2 and Q3 turn on to conduct current. The conduction for both directions of inductor current $I_L > 0$ and $I_L < 0$. During interval four, the inductor current continues to be negative. During this interval, the voltage across the primary is $-V_1$ and, and the voltage across the secondary is $-V_2$. The difference in these voltages, which is $(-V_1+V_2)$, appears across the inductor. Hence, the current ramps down with a negative slope as shown in Equation.

$$\left(\frac{di}{dt}\right) = \frac{V_1 - V_2}{L}$$

During this interval, switches Q2 and Q3 continue to remain turned on, but as the voltage across the secondary are now $-V_2$, switches Q6 and Q7 turn on to conduct current as shown in Fig. 2.

B. Control Methods

In the proposed SPWM strategy, the duty cycle of only a single active bridge is adjusted while that of another bridge is fixed. The biggest advantage of this method is that the ZVS range of the DAB converter can be considerably expanded, and the circulating current can be reduced, so that low conduction and switching losses are achieved.

The step-down operation in this report means that the secondary output voltage V_{dc2} is less than the input voltage V_{dc1} . Define the duty cycles of the primary and secondary bridges in the DAB converter as follows:

$$d_{pri} = \frac{1}{2} - \frac{\alpha}{2\pi}$$

$$d_{sec} = \frac{1}{2} - \frac{\beta}{2\pi}$$

Fig. 3 illustrates typical waveforms under the proposed SPWM operation. For step- down operation, α is adjusted so that the duty cycle of V_{pri} varies while β has the value of zero. This means that d_{sec} is fixed at 0.5 with a no zero voltage interval in V_{sec} . This is a rather different operating scheme when compared to traditional PSM, where both V_{pri} and V_{sec} have 0.5 of a duty cycle. Another control parameter in the proposed SPWM is the phase difference ϕ between V_{pri} and V_{sec} . In addition ϕ is defined as the phase difference between the fundamentals of V_{pri} and V_{sec} , and following relationship is derived by

$$\varphi = \varphi_f - \frac{\alpha}{2}$$

By transferring the zero-output power, ϕ should be zero. since power is transferred from the primary side to the secondary side, $I_{d1} \leq 0$, $I_{d2} \geq 0$, and $I_{d3} \geq 0$.

Fig. 3 SPWM for a) step down operation b) step up operation

Here the input voltage V_{dc1} is fixed, and the output voltage V_{dc2} is controlled to be higher than the V_{dc1} . This means that the direction of the power flow is from the primary side to the secondary side. Unlike the step-down operation, the duty cycle of the primary voltage is fixed at 0.5 and the secondary side duty cycle is changed. It should be noted here that α is zero and β is adjusted. The PSM technique always has a phase difference of $\phi \geq 0$ in the operating region. However in case of single- PWM, there is a region with a phase difference of $\phi < 0$ for the low power region because the PWM control is applied. For this reason, an additional analysis of this region is also needed. As can be seen in fig b) the figure represents the case of a phase difference of $\phi < 0$.

III.SIMULATION RESULTS

The Bidirectional Dual Active Bridge Converter is designed, and the corresponding design parameters listed out in Table 1. The higher switching frequency reduces the size of the reactive component if we go with hardware implementation, so the switching frequency is set to 100KHz. The designed circuit is simulated using MATLAB.

TABLE I
BIDIRECTIONAL DUAL ACTIVE BRIDGE CONVERTER SPECIFICATIONS

PARAMETERS	VALUES
INPUT VOLTAGE	750 V
OUTPUT VOLTAGE	540 - 720 V
LEAKAGE INDUCTANCE	300 μ F
SWITCHING FREQUENCY	100KHz
URNS RATIO	1:1

Fig. 4 a) Input/output voltage b) Input/output current for the duty cycle of 0.5.

Fig. 5 Waveform for leakage inductor current

Fig. 6 Switching Pattern

The input /output voltage and input /output current for the duty cycle of 0.5 are shown in Fig 4. In these plots both the input and output voltages are maintained as constant. The phase shift between the two bridges are maintained at 10° . It is observed that for input voltage of 750 V the input current is 2A and the desired output current is 10 A, and the current leakage through the inductor is around 80A. The switching pattern of eight switches with the phase shift of 10 degrees across the two bridges are shown in Fig 6. The performance analysis are as shown in Fig. 7. It is clearly noted down that the efficiency almost remains constant for the load variation of 4 to 20 A and the input variation 2 to 12 A.

Fig. 7 Efficiency plot for load and line variation

IV. CONCLUSION

The SPWM method is used to provide soft-switching in the whole operating range by choosing and to reduce conduction loss by the PWM technique at low loads. The performance of the proposed strategy was verified using a 10KW DAB converter. The system efficiency is increased from 85% to 95%. In addition, the strategy can be used to optimize the DAB system design. In this work, a dual active bridge is identified as a preferred power converter for interfacing the low voltage and high voltage dc busses due to its potential high power capacity and bidirectional power flow capabilities.

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